

DARE UK **PANORAMA**
A DARE UK PROJECT

Output Statistical Disclosure Control (OSDC) Principles to support Federated Analytics across Trusted Research Environments

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PANORAMA Work Package 3 Deliverable

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Executive Summary

Output Statistical Disclosure Control (OSDC) is an essential process within Trusted Research Environments (TREs) to protect the confidentiality of data processed by its researchers, providing a balance of secure data protection whilst enabling research. The disclosure control rules, set by organisations, are a vital part of the Five Safes framework (UK Data Service), enforced to satisfy 'Safe Outputs' - where only reviewed and approved outputs of aggregate, non-disclosive, data can be released from the secure environment. Each secure environment may apply different rules of thumb to prevent the risk of disclosure, this presents a unique issue when considering supporting federated analytics, as organisations may have the same 'principles' but different 'rules'.

This document proposes principles for federated OSDC to combat this issue and support federated analysis, irrespective of whether the organisations do or do not have (semi-)automated disclosure checking tools implemented e.g., SACRO (Semi-Automated Checking of

Research Outputs) (Smith *et al.*, 2023). The principles are designed to address the disclosure gap, and other challenges, that can be present in a proposed federated analytics model, by suggesting areas of discussion, supporting conversations, and aiding decision making. The principles also provide a structured pathway for organisations to align OSDC practices, evaluating two primary operating models:

1. **Without an Aggregator:** Where each safe environment independently applies agreed upon OSDC to outputs, prior to release.
2. **With an Aggregator:** Where a lead organisation (Aggregator) combines results from each site before applying agreed upon OSDC centrally for the release of outputs, aiming to reduce administrative burden and increase statistical utility for researchers.

1. Purpose and Scope

This document recognises the challenges faced by organisations that support, are piloting, or wish to support, federated analysis within a Secure Data Environment, Trusted Research Environment or Safe Haven (hereafter referred to as secure environment(s)), where the projects utilising these services are analysing sensitive, anonymised and/or pseudonymised, individual-level, and predominantly unconsented data. The principles outline what organisations should discuss, agree upon, and operationalise in relation to OSDC for federated analysis. This framework assumes that; the Information Governance (IG), such as establishing equivalency, and the technical infrastructure capabilities for federated querying and/or (semi)-automated OSDC tooling to support federated analysis have already been agreed upon by organisations. However, governance and technical aspects are lightly discussed within this document around workflow and operationalisation of federated OSDC. The design of these principles has been built upon 1) lived-in experiences and contributions of those actively, or previously, conducting OSDC within safe environment(s), 2) the challenges of OSDC within existing processes that a federated model could alleviate, 3) concerns of federated model OSDC feasibility, and 4) contributions from organisations where OSDC is in the early stages of implementation.

2. Background

2.1. What is Output Statistical Disclosure Control (OSDC)?

The development of output statistical disclosure control (OSDC) began in the early 2000s, evaluating the residual risk that exists from statistical outputs, with potential to breach confidentiality. As the concept of secure environments progressed and became operational, OSDC has been implemented within organisations to protect the sensitive data they hold. This consists of both *input statistical disclosure control*, i.e., removing identifiable information from a data extraction prior to the researcher(s) obtaining access to that data, such as names and date of birth; and *output statistical disclosure control (OSDC)*, i.e., the controls to ensure data

egressed from the secure environment does not breach confidentiality, such as ensuring minimum count thresholds are adhered to, and that no individual patient level data is contained within an output. Although organisations may apply different rules to their OSDC processes, and produce guidance for researchers, the main comprehensive guide referenced within the UK is from the Secure Data Access Professionals (SDAP) expert group (SDAP, 2024). There are other published guidelines, such as from NHS England Digital, which outlines SDC that should be applied to Hospital Episode Statistics (HES) and Emergency Care Data Set (ECDS), which organisations providing access to these datasets abide by (NHS England Digital, 2023). Organisations' OSDC guidance is generally provided to researchers via a handbook, or intranet, and occasionally publicly available (UK Data Service, 2025)

2.2. OSDC workflow in practice

Although organisations may apply varied rules to their OSDC practices, the end-to-end workflow for a researcher to request an output is more aligned. **Figure 1** illustrates the high-level stages of requesting an output to be released from the secure environment. Researchers will first submit their request, typically via email or automated request service, for review by a trained member of staff from the secure environment. At first review, the reviewer will check the request against their existing OSDC rules. Typically, a reviewer first checks that the minimum count threshold has been adhered to, and highlights any instances where this has been missed. Next assessing if there is any class disclosure within the request, where all or none of the observations fit into a category (Green *et al.*, 2020), inferring that an individual fits into a category without that specific individual being identified. Alongside class disclosure, the reviewer should assess for secondary disclosure, a process where two or more pieces of information can be combined to reveal disclosive information. For example, if a count table has had all of the less than minimum threshold counts removed, but the row or column totals remain and these totals can be subtracted from one another to reveal what the removed below minimum counts are. This is an extremely difficult type of disclosure to eradicate, especially when considering outputs that have already been released from the secure environment. The first reviewer will also carry out administrative checks such as ensuring the requested analysis aligns with the approved research proposal and governance in place for the project.

Once these steps are completed, the first reviewer will assess whether the request has passed the disclosure controls or not. If the request has passed, the reviewer will determine if a subsequent review is needed or not. A subsequent review will often involve the same disclosure and administrative checks as the first review, or this will be a shorter limited sense check. Some organisations have a subsequent review implemented into their processes as standard to adopt the Four-Eyes Principle (UNIDO), whereas others do not require an additional review if the request passes disclosure control. Where requests do not require a subsequent review, the first reviewer will prepare the requested files for release to the researcher via their internal processes. If the first reviewer deems that the request has not passed the disclosure controls, they will report this to the researcher with recommended amendments to be implemented. After the recommendations have been addressed by the

researcher, the request will be subsequently reviewed against the same disclosure and administrative checks as required. Subsequent reviews follow the same workflow of approval to release of the requested output, or further recommended iteration feedback to the researcher. Some organisations may allow for unlimited revisions to an output request before release, whilst others will have a limit applied where if the request does not satisfy the disclosure controls within that limit then it will be rejected entirely. Rejection may also occur if there are significant changes that must be implemented in order to meet disclosure controls, and the researcher would be required to submit a new request once those changes have been met.

Output Statistical Disclosure Control Workflow

Figure 1. High-level workflow of tasks conducted during OSDC from a secure environment.

2.3. What is federated analysis?

Federated analysis is a process where data requested from multiple organisations, by a research team, remains within each host organisation, and the researcher(s) sends their written code to each site to be run on the requested data. This is often referred to as ‘Eyes-off’ analysis, as the researcher(s) do not directly access the data at each site. Federated analysis can involve the researcher(s) writing their code within one of the secure environments against

one cohort, for the code to subsequently be sent to the other secure environment(s) and run against an equivalent cohort(s). **Figure 2** (below), produced by the TRE-FX project, illustrates how the researcher(s) code is distributed to each site, and aggregated data (combined, summary data) is returned to the researcher(s) (TRE-FX, 2023). It is therefore critical that a federation produces consistent outputs to align with those produced by the research team.

Figure 2. Flow of researcher code and aggregate data within federated analytics (TRE-FX, 2023, Available at: <https://trefx.uk/federated-analytics>)

2.4. The benefits of federation

The benefits of a federated analytics approach include:

- Avoiding complicated and lengthy governance processes that are required when pooling data from multiple organisations into a single site, e.g., multiple Data Sharing Agreements (DSAs) and Data Privacy Impact Assessments (DPIAs).
- The data controllers remain in full control of the data, who can access it, and how it is used.
- Mitigation of technical issues that could arise when transferring data between organisations.
- Increasing sample size for the researcher's cohort of interest, particularly when researching rare conditions.
- Reduced cost to the researcher for analysing a larger cohort versus conducting pooled analysis in relation to typical storage costs.

- Eliminating storage constraints that a single site could incur for pooled analysis.

2.5. The challenges of federation

The common challenges of a federated analytics approach include:

- 'Eyes Off' analysis - the researcher does not get to see the data at each site, meaning they cannot validate whether the data curated has what they need to address their research question(s).
- Federated querying against data that lacks harmonisation across organisations due to the data structure.
- Concern that analysing data separately, and combining the aggregate outputs, loses statistical significance to the data.
- Aligning existing OSDC practices across organisations, i.e., differences in acceptable versus unacceptable outputs.

2.6. The need for principles

These principles work to address the need for consistency across a federation in organisational processes and outcomes related to OSDC. For example, one organisation does not release (or withhold) outputs that another organisation, within the federation, would release (or withhold).

3. The OSDC Principles

The OSDC Federation Principles outlines the foundational aspects that organisations must collectively address to support federated analytics, including reviewing existing procedures, choosing a federation model, considering the use of (semi)- automated tooling, determining a federated OSDC standard, and its implementation. Before organisations discuss the individual aspects of this suggested approach, they should each evaluate their current processes for pooled analysis. Establishing where organisations are deemed equivalent or where distinct differences occur, can aid conversations regarding working within a federation model. Operational differences must be addressed to prevent incompatible release decisions, risk of disclosure, or unsustainable workload across each site.

3.1. Choosing an OSDC federation model

When considering federated statistical disclosure control of research outputs, organisations should firstly agree upon their federation model, which details the point(s) at which OSDC methodology is applied to the output(s). Currently, the typical federation model proposed in pilot work is in the absence of an Aggregator; both this model and one with the inclusion of an Aggregator are outlined below.

3.1.1. Application of OSDC in a Federation Model without an Aggregator

The typical federation model is without the presence of an Aggregator, where each secure environment within the federation would implement the agreed upon technical infrastructure and (semi)-automated SDC tools (if any), and conduct OSDC methodology to their own summary results that are produced by the federated querying, prior to transferring these data back to the researcher(s). **Figure 2A**, in section 2.1.2, highlights the point(s) at which OSDC is applied in both a federated model with and without an Aggregator. With this model, it is imperative that each organisation implements the agreed upon SDC methodology consistently, ensuring harmonisation of summary data. The model without an Aggregator may be preferred by Data Controllers as disclosure risks within the summary results are mitigated before the data is transferred and returned to the researcher(s). Additionally, this model may be selected if none of the secure environments within the federation have the capacity to act as an Aggregator, as this responsibility requires additional resources that are subsequently outlined within this framework.

3.1.2. Application of OSDC in a federation Model with an Aggregator

An Aggregator is one organisation, within the federation, that is responsible for collecting the summary data from each secure environment, combining these data, and subsequently applying the agreed OSDC methodology e.g., minimum count threshold, low number suppression etc. This produces one larger set of summary results that is returned to the researcher(s).

Figure 2A. An amended diagram from Figure 2 (TRE-FX, 2023), illustrating the point of OSDC application (green circles), and points where OSDC is not applied (red crosses). Model A – Without an Aggregator shows OSDC application from each site, whereas Model B – With an Aggregator shows OSDC is only applied at one site, once the summary outputs from each site have been combined.

There are many envisioned benefits from the Aggregator model, such as reduced workload for each secure environment, as they are not required to conduct manual OSDC (that is often time consuming), nor are they required to implement (semi)-automated tooling within their infrastructure. Each secure environment is assured that the chosen OSDC methodology is applied consistently to all the data requested. Additionally, some information governance hurdles may be lessened, as despite data still being transferred between organisations, the data is aggregated and therefore may satisfy differing risk appetites. Electing an Aggregator also has the benefit of delivering a single output of data to the researcher(s), alleviating them of combining summary results. Conversely, some Data Controllers may have concerns around the transfer of potential below threshold data between organisations. This possibility should be discussed in detail as to whether specific clauses within agreements (e.g., Data Sharing Agreement(s)) need to be defined to allow transfer of such data, particularly with Information Governance colleagues and Data Controllers.

The elected Aggregator may be the organisation where the researcher(s) accesses one set of data, for building their code. Or it may be elected for being resource rich, allowing easier and quicker implementation and execution of the chosen OSDC methodology. Alternatively, it may be elected if the organisation holds metadata that allows data harmonisation of each set of summary results.

3.1.3. Adoption of (semi)-automated tooling

Currently, there is early adoption and testing of (semi)-automated tools for OSDC across secure environments in the UK, including testing conducted within another PANORAMA work package. However, many organisations rely on manual OSDC processes to prevent disclosure risk. Manual checks can be resource-heavy and time-consuming, with the added element of human error and the inevitable possibility of releasing a research output that breaches confidentiality. Although (semi)-automated tools could tackle human error risks, the tools cannot conduct OSDC on every type of potential analysis, ultimately requiring manual checks regardless of implementation. Additionally, the administrative tasks that accompany OSDC, i.e., ensuring the requested analysis aligns with the approved research protocol, cannot be performed by semi-automated tooling. And so, in the current landscape these tools will likely aid, rather than replace, manual OSDC processes.

To aid the process, a federation may choose to adopt an existing (semi)-automated tool to reduce the workload of manual checks, by acting as one set of eyes within the 'Four-Eyes principle', and allow more efficient turnaround of requested outputs. To consider the potential of such tooling, each organisation could gather evidence of the types of outputs typically requested, and the associated resource requirements to conduct OSDC according to their current processes. This could quantify the usefulness of adopting such a tool to the organisation to reduce workload. Additionally, the organisation(s) could assess the tools' current capabilities and harness these by adapting their existing documentation and guidance to levy on such capabilities. For example, if an organisation discovered that a tool could be applied against twenty-five percent of their typical output requests (e.g., frequency tables), but require the tool to be capable of being applied to at least fifty percent of outputs in order to

support the adoption of the tool, they may choose to amend their guidance for researchers, encouraging outputs in a specific format e.g., frequency tables, to allow faster release of requested outputs.

3.2. Determining Statistical Disclosure Control methodology

Traditional OSDC methods include techniques such as, cell suppression, thresholding, noise addition, and combination of counts. Defining what is allowed and prohibited within an output request from researchers is essential to maintaining consistency across the federation. This should encompass approved file types, minimum count thresholds, safe vs. unsafe outputs, etc. The federation may be required to follow existing rules on statistical output control, based upon the information governance in place and the data used for analysis, such as the NHS England Digital Disclosure Control methodology for Hospital Episode Statistics (HES) and Emergency Care Data Set (ECDS) (NHS England, 2023). If the organisations are not required to follow existing rules, or guidance, they may still electively choose to follow already published guidance, such as the Safe Data Access Professionals SDC Handbook (SDAP, 2020) or the Statbarn model (Green *et al.*, 2024).

3.2.1. Outlining existing OSDC Methodology, Administrative procedures, and limiting factors

Despite each secure environment likely following the same, or similar, principles of OSDC e.g., having a threshold and methods of suppression, it is just as likely that the organisations apply different rules to these principles e.g., varying threshold limits. Mapping existing processes can illustrate equivalence and differences across organisations in a tangible way for further dissection. If the organisations all apply a minimum count threshold, but this threshold varies, the discussion should expand to the justification for each threshold. If one of the organisations is bound by existing standards, such as the NHS England Digital Disclosure Control methodology (2023) described above, then the other organisations would likely need to agree that those guidelines will be adopted for the purpose of a federated project. If none of the organisations rely on existing guidance, but have varying minimum thresholds, each organisation should provide their justification for their standard and agree upon a minimum satisfactory standard for all parties. This may require conversation with Information Governance representatives, or Data Controllers, regarding what would be deemed as acceptable and satisfactory. From the opinion-discovery interviews held for this deliverable, it was suggested that the highest threshold, held by an organisation, should be applied to federated projects to reduce disclosure risk i.e., if the organisations have minimum thresholds of 5, 7, and 10 respectively, then for federated projects a minimum threshold of 10 should be adopted. Where a proposed federation would include an Aggregator, it may be considered that the existing OSDC methodology of the organisation acting as the Aggregator will be followed, if mutually agreed.

Similarly, acceptable ways for how to tackle disclosure issues should be discussed e.g., rounding counts, combining categories, and removal and/or replacing of below threshold counts, to protect confidentiality. The current processes can be mapped and justified to allow

an agreed upon standard to be developed. For some organisations, they may have existing processes that apply different methods of tackling disclosure based upon; 1) the datasets used; 2) the sensitivity of the data; 3) the research question addressed. For example, research into rare conditions, where cohorts are expected to be small, or analysis containing special category data under GDPR, where the data is highly sensitive, may come with additional stipulation for OSDC from organisations, data controllers, or approval bodies. In these instances, the proposed federation could agree upon a tiered system of addressing disclosure concerns and a supplementary process for escalation. For example, applying more stringent OSDC and mitigation methods to high-risk projects, i.e., a higher minimum count threshold, and complete removal of below-threshold counts respectively.

Organisations must consider that OSDC is more than simply applying principles and rules to statistical outputs, and that these are accompanied by administrative checks on outputs. These often include ensuring the requested output aligns with the approved research protocol and objectives, comparison to previous approved outputs to prevent differential disclosure, and ensuring the output is deemed 'publishable'. In general, 'publishable' outputs include journal or working papers, policy reports, and interim reports, amongst others. Organisations often do not release interim results that may be used for regular research team meetings and encourage alternative methods for discussing such results. For the successful implementation of OSDC within a federation, organisations should map their existing administrative processes and expectations from researchers regarding publishable outputs and mutually agree upon the standards to be adopted within the federation.

3.3. Operationalising OSDC procedures within the federated model

3.3.1. Implementation of federated OSDC methodology

Once organisations have discussed their existing procedures for OSDC of pooled analysis research outputs, acknowledged any limiting factors, and agreed upon OSDC principles and/or rules for the federation the proposed OSDC methodology should be formalised into a Federated Operating Manual, or such like. This should describe the federated model, agreed upon OSDC methodology, organisational expectations and responsibilities, as well as the Information Governance and Technical requirements for the federation to operate. The detailed OSDC methodology should explicitly describe the agreed-upon thresholds, methods of tackling disclosure issues, safe vs. unsafe outputs and/or file types, and the escalation process of high-risk projects. This will ensure that researchers receive harmonised data outputs that are easy to integrate, particularly if an Aggregator is not adopted.

Other specific areas for consideration, that complement OSDC methodology and should be integrated into a Federated Operating Manual, are outlined below.

3.3.2. Accountability

The federation must determine the site which has overall accountability for maintaining confidentiality within requested outputs, with note to the process for if there is a breach in

disclosure. Traditionally, the host organisation is accountable for the safety of the data it holds, with a responsibility to report disclosure breaches to the appropriate Data Controller(s). It should be considered whether each site is ultimately responsible for their own outputs, or whether one organisation has greater accountability than the others – particularly if an Aggregator is adopted within the federation model.

3.3.3. Training Standards

To ensure integrity across the Federation, organisations should take particular interest in aligning training standards, first assessing equivalency in existing expectations i.e., determining whether different training programmes cover the same Learning Outcomes (LOs), and if this is satisfactory across the federation. It is important that organisations consider training for both researchers and staff conducting OSDC, and whether they will set ‘Gold Standard’ requirements for training, or if multiple courses will be accepted if they cover the necessary LOs.

- **For researchers:** Existing training requirements for those accessing data within each secure environment should be outlined to determine where there are equivalency or distinct training gaps that need to be addressed. If researchers will be accessing data within one site and using (semi)-automated tooling for a ‘first look’ at their output request, do they require specific training on how to 1) write code appropriately for federated analytics, and 2) use the (semi)-automated tooling.
- **For staff conducting OSDC:** Currently, secure environments across the UK have varying requirements for staff training of those conducting OSDC as part of their role. These include on-the-job training, previous experience, e-Learning / online courses (e.g., Safe Researcher Training), or in-person courses. The SDC-REBOOT Community, a DARE UK community group, has a focus on standards and best practice for OSDC, but requirements across the UK are still vastly varied. In a similar sense to researcher training considerations, organisations should determine where their staff training requirements are equivalent and where distinct gaps occur. Aligning staff training for OSDC implementation will ensure the production of consistent outputs. Some organisations may feel comfortable for staff across the sites to not hold the same training requirements, as long as the agreed upon OSDC is followed uniformly across sites.

3.3.4. Auditing

To ensure sustainability of the federation, not only do organisations need to align in information governance, technical capabilities, and OSDC methodology and implementation, they must also agree upon an auditing mechanism for OSDC. The auditing should cover several aspects:

- **Audit Trail:** Where it is determined which pieces of information must be recorded for each output request through the OSDC process. This could include details of the type of analysis, file type, resource requirement, which OSDC rules were applied,

suppression or mitigation of disclosure concerns, where (semi)-automated tools were applied, and whether the request was escalated, rejected or approved.

- **Peer Review:** To ensure consistency in applying the agreed upon OSDC, organisations should peer review a sample of the output requests from each site at regular intervals e.g., quarterly / bi-annually. In the inception of a federated model, it is suggested that there be more frequent cross-site peer review, which progressively lessens over time. If significant discrepancies are found, where one organisation is being particularly lenient (or overly stringent) versus the agreed OSDC, then the organisations should discuss this in detail, and reassess the Federated Operating Manual, if necessary.
- **Transparency:** There should be consideration to how transparent auditing activities can be to stakeholders. For example, where (semi)-automated tooling is present, the built-in automated logs could be utilised to fulfil audit trail needs, and be regularly available to Data Controllers, or other sites within the federation, to ensure automated rules are applied consistently e.g., the minimum count threshold. Additionally, to promote public trust, a summary of audit activities could be made available via an open-source website or platform. For example, a quarterly update that states the number of outputs requested and checked against the OSDC methodology within the period, the percentage of those that were rejected and for which reasons.

4. Further Research

These principles have been designed to progress federated analytics across secure environments, provide a backbone for OSDC methodology within proposed federations, and to aid conversations as the appetite to support federated analytics within the UK grows. However, this preliminary output has highlighted areas for continued research into how OSDC should be addressed for a federated project. The areas of further interest include assessing the appetite landscape from not just organisations, but researchers for federated 'Eyes-off' analytics; and comparing the prospects of piloting federated analytics versus enhancing the facilitation of pooled analysis.

4.1. Testing the waters: Evaluating researcher appetite and perceived value

This output was limited by focusing on the anticipated benefits to secure environments for supporting federated analytics, through existing review of research, contributions from secure environments, and lived-in experiences. From review of the existing research, and the undertaking of PPPIE as another deliverable within the PANORAMA project, much stakeholder engagement has centred around organisations that could be defined as secure environments, data controllers, and public engagement. Although this is crucial to understand how feasible supporting federated analytics is with health and social care data providers, and the patients' whose data are used, there is limited research investigating researcher appetite and perceived value of federated analytics. A deep-dive evaluation into the anticipated benefits of federated

analytics to researchers, mapping their concerns, and how these can be addressed, could greatly enrich existing research.

The SDE network in England is in its infancy, launched in 2023, with the individual SDEs at varying points within their set up and operationalisation. With this, the concept of secure data access and application of OSDC methodology will be new to many researchers within England. Particularly with those who have not analysed data where OSDC has been applied previously, or who access routine health and social care data as part of their job but have not used these data within a research context. This represents an opportunity to gather opinions, concerns and feedback from researchers currently using, or endeavouring to access, data within a secure environment. Mirroring this evaluation with researchers in Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland, where safe data access organisations have been well operationalised, would allow insightful comparisons to whether researchers' perceived value and/or concerns of federation overlap. Comparisons of particular interest could review; 1) the level of researcher experience, 2) type(s) of data accessed by researchers and, 3) organisational structure and expertise of the data access provider(s). Outputs of this work could further highlight areas of focus for progressing federated research across secure environments, such as building a framework to satisfy researcher concerns.

4.2. A rock and a hard place: Piloting federated analytics vs. enhanced facilitation of pooled analysis

Feedback obtained during online opinion-discovery interviews highlighted significant reservations from organisations about supporting federated analytics due to unique existing OSDC methodology and administrative processes that would be difficult to adapt to a federation model. This subsequently sparked conversation into how pooled analysis could be better enabled across the health and social care data space, to support research. The challenges of pooled analysis have been well reported, and how federated analytics can combat these (Wolfson *et al.*, 2010). However, further research into comparing pilot federation projects with an enhanced facilitation of data sharing for pooled analysis pipeline, could reveal the potential avenues for the progression of data access for research across the UK. Which would be particularly significant for organisations that would have difficulty in supporting federated projects, whether in relation to existing processes, risk appetite, or resource or technological restrictions.

4.3. Other areas for consideration

As suggested in section “2.2.1 *Outlining existing OSDC Methodology, Administrative Procedures, and Limiting Factors*” of this output, organisations bound by existing OSDC guidelines would likely be the denominator for OSDC methodology to support a federated project. Additional work in establishing NHS England Digital's perspective on this theme would be insightful to determine if federated projects using Hospital Episode Statistics (HES) and Emergency Care Data Set (ECDS) could be subject to different OSDC methodology when working with other organisations. In conjunction, further recommendations include discovery work with data controllers on; 1) their perception and concerns on the concept of adopting the strictest OSDC

methodology present within a proposed federation and, 2) the concept of adopting an Aggregator.

4. Conclusions

From the development of these principles, there is evidently a growing appetite to support federated analytics across organisations within the UK. With particular interest in the avoidance in complex, and lengthy, governance processes that coincide with pooled analysis, and how (semi)-automated tooling could aid OSDC, reducing workload and improving the turnaround time of requested outputs. Despite acknowledging the advantages of utilising (semi)-automated tools for OSDC, organisations have reservations over how to ensure the accompanying administrative processes are adhered to.

For the OSDC aspect of federated analytics to be successful and sustainable, organisations must be willing to openly discuss their existing processes, risk appetite, and reservations (if any). This should be used as an aid to provide structure for conversations as the federation develops. It is recommended that further research into stakeholder opinions on the individual aspects proposed, and how it could be developed further would be beneficial for the overall landscape progression of federated analytics within the UK.

Acknowledgements

The PANORAMA project was funded as part of the UKRI DARE UK – Phase 2 (UKRI Data and Analytics Research Environments UK- Phase 2) programme. DARE UK – Phase 2 is funded by the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Programme; and Phase 2 is delivered jointly by HDR UK, and ADR UK, and funded by UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Fund.

The authors are grateful to those who have contributed to this output, either via participation at online opinion-discovery interviews, or providing written comment to an earlier draft of this output.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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